

Effect of powder origin on densification, microstructure and ball-on-three-balls strength of hydroxyapatite ceramics.

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ABSTRACT

Hydroxyapatite ceramics require not only biocompatibility but also high mechanical reliability, while the effect of powder origin remains insufficiently understood. This study evaluated four hydroxyapatite powder systems: three commercial powders with different morphology, phase composition, and flow behaviour, and one 1:1 blended powder. Disc specimens were fabricated by uniaxial pressing and pressureless sintering at 1300 °C for 1 h, followed by phase, density, microstructural, fractographic, Young's modulus, and B3B strength analyses with Weibull statistics. Powder origin strongly affected compaction, densification, porosity, and mechanical performance. The spray-dried HA-A powder achieved the best properties, with a characteristic strength of ~108 MPa, Weibull modulus of 24, density of 2.87 g·cm⁻³, and Young's modulus of ~91 GPa, whereas HA-B and HA-C showed significantly lower strengths (~37–39 MPa) due to higher porosity. The HA-D blend retained high strength (~107 MPa), demonstrating that suitable powder design can preserve mechanical reliability despite partial incorporation of lower-quality powder.

Keywords: Hydroxyapatite, Powder processing, Densification, Microstructure, Biaxial strength

1 INTRODUCTION

The mechanical properties of bone are governed by both composition and a complex microstructure that includes density, porosity, degree of mineralisation, bone architecture, collagen fibre orientation, and collagen crosslinking. Porosity is one of the key factors influencing bone strength, as illustrated by the difference between dense cortical bone and porous trabecular bone. [1], [2], [3]. The typical range of apparent density for cortical bone is 1.8–2.0 g·cm⁻³ compared to approximately 1.0–1.4 g·cm⁻³ for trabecular bone. This decrease in apparent density is primarily due to the presence of marrow-filled spaces. By contrast, the density of the calcified matrix of trabecular bone is comparable to that of compact bone [4].

The mechanical properties of bone have long been evaluated by a range of experimental techniques that reflect the heterogeneous nature of natural tissues. Specimens are typically loaded to failure in compression, tension, torsion, or bending. When combined with mathematical and engineering models, such as finite element (FE) simulations tailored to specimen geometry, boundary conditions, and

loading configurations, these tests can be used to estimate tissue-level material properties. Bailey and Vasishth [5] reviewed methods for the mechanical characterization of bone with respect to both the types of experiments performed and the interpretation of the resulting data. They considered not only the test methods themselves, but also the scale of investigation, from the mesoscale to the nanoscale. The mechanical behaviour of whole bone is commonly assessed under axial (compressive or tensile), bending, or torsional loading, either under monotonic or cyclic conditions. Similar approaches are widely used for synthetic biomaterials intended for tissue engineering. Turner and Burr [6] also highlighted the need to evaluate a broader set of mechanical parameters than strength and Young's modulus alone, while emphasizing the importance of reliable test methods, validation procedures, and proper sample storage and preparation. The bending test is considered the most useful test for determining the mechanical properties of whole cortical bones or small bones, which are very difficult to machine [7], [8]. In contrast, the compression test is commonly used for the biomechanical assessment, such as stiffness and strength of spongy trabecular bone [9], [10]. Three-point and four-point bending tests are commonly used to evaluate the flexural strength of biomaterials. Because bone consists primarily of collagen and hydroxyapatite (HA), analogous test methods are standardized for both plastics [11] or [12] and ceramic materials [13] to ensure consistent measurement procedures. Over the last two to three decades, however, there has been a growing trend toward the use of biaxial loading methods, especially for brittle materials such as ceramics. They offer advantages such as simple specimen geometry, elimination of both the stress concentration and machining defects at edges, and easier sample preparation (e.g. disk shape) than for uniaxial tests. In addition, biaxial loading is often more representative of practical service conditions. Common biaxial test configurations include ring-on-ring, pin-on-ring, ball-on-ring, piston-on-three-balls, and ball-on-three-balls (B3B) [14], [15]. Although the phase and chemical composition of biomaterials are often reported in detail, much less attention is usually paid to powder characteristics such as flow behaviour and compressibility, particularly when components are produced by cold pressing. Powders are highly functional materials with a wide range of useful properties, but they can also be difficult to process. Their behaviour is complex and may change even with minor variations in ambient conditions. A sound understanding of powder behaviour is therefore essential to avoid problems such as sticking to processing equipment, electrostatic charging, or performance changes during prolonged or high-intensity mixing. If powder properties are not properly characterized, they can easily compromise both production efficiency and final product quality.

In this work, three commercial hydroxyapatite powders and one blend were used to prepare disc-shaped specimens for the evaluation of mechanical properties under biaxial flexure loading by the B3B method. The specimens were sintered at 1300 °C for 1 h, selected based on the best biocompatibility response in cytotoxicity testing [16]. The strength of the as-sintered hydroxyapatite bioceramics was evaluated using Weibull statistics in relation to powder origin, bulk density, and microstructure. The results highlight the importance of powder characteristics, including particle size, particle size distribution, and flow behaviour on final mechanical properties observed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PART

2.1 Material preparation

Three different commercially available powders were used for uniaxial cold pressing of disks (**Figure 1**): Tricafos 500 (marked as “HA-A”), Cafos M (Budenheim, Germany) (marked as “HA-B”) and HSYC (Huangshi Yucheng Trade Co., LTD, China) (marked as powder/samples “HA-C”)

Figure 1 Photographs of the commercial powders used in this work: Budenheim, Germany Tricafos 500 (HA-A) and Cafos M (HA-B); and HSYC (HA-C) from Huangshi Yucheng Trade Co., Ltd., China.

The true density of the material for each powder was determined using a Quantachrome Ultrapyc 1200e pycnometer. The average values found were 3.0449 g.cm^{-3} for HA-A, 2.9412 g.cm^{-3} for HA-B, and 2.8693 g.cm^{-3} for HA-C. Particle size distribution was measured using a Malvern Mastersizer MS3000 analyser. The results are summarized in **Table 1** and illustrated in **Figure 2**. The HA-B and HA-C powders show a similar particle size distribution curve compared to the HA-A powder, whose distribution is bimodal with two maxima distinguished. The first at a particle/granule size of approximately $\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$ and the second at $\sim 110 \mu\text{m}$ to $120 \mu\text{m}$.

Table 1 Particle size distribution of the HA powders measured using a Malvern Mastersizer MS3000 analyser.

	<i>D</i> 10 (μm)	<i>D</i> 50 (μm)	<i>D</i> 90 (μm)
HA-A	2.96	36.70	151.00
HA-B	1.19	4.30	12.30
HA-C	1.94	5.57	13.50

Figure 2 Particle size distribution of corresponding HA samples measured using a Malvern Mastersizer MS3000 analyzer.

The flow properties of all three powders were characterized using an FT4 Powder Rheometer® (Freeman Technology, UK). The motion behaviour of the powder material was characterized based on the flow functions. The flow function parameter ffc is defined as

$$ffc = \frac{MPS}{UYS} \quad (1)$$

where MPS (kPa) is the major principal stress and UYS (kPa) is the unconfined yield strength (kPa) measured during the shear test. Based on the value of ffc , the flow properties of the powders can be classified as follows: 0-1, non-flowing; 1-2, very cohesive; 2-4, cohesive; 4-10, easy-flowing; and >10, free-flowing (**Figure 3**).

Figure 3 Flow functions of the HA powders measured using the Freeman Technology Powder Rheometer instrument.

In addition, sample internal friction angles are shown in **Figure 4** with distinct differences detected. The angle of internal friction AIF ($^{\circ}$) was evaluated as a function of the initial consolidation stress IS (kPa).

Figure 4 Angles of internal friction of HA powders measured using the Freeman Technology Powder Rheometer instrument.

To determine powder flow characteristics as influenced by other powder characteristics such as size and shape, surface area, material density, and powder cohesion, the Hausner ratio was measured using a Sotax TD1 tapped density tester. The Hausner ratio (HR) was calculated from the untapped and tapped bulk volume of a powder. The calculated values were 1.220 for HA-A powder, indicating *fair flow character*, and 1.667 for both HA-B and HA-C powders, corresponding to *very poor flow character* [17]. These results supported the previous results of the flow functions for the HA powders.

Generally, a free-flowing powder such as HA-A powder can be distributed more uniformly in the steel die and, owing to its granule morphology, should be readily well compressible. The applied pressure promotes granule breakdown, particle rearrangement into a near close-packed configuration, and thus more uniform compaction. By contrast, the ungranulated HA-B and HA-C powders are more cohesive (**Figure 3**), which increases die-wall friction and reduces pressure transmission, leading to uneven compaction at the bottom of the tablet than at the top. In addition, the high surface area of nano- or submicron-powders promotes the formation of natural agglomerates, resulting in poorer particle rearrangement in the die. Higher pressures are therefore often required for nanopowders than for micrometre-sized powders. [18]. Among all three investigated powders, HA-B exhibited the highest internal friction angle across the entire range of initial consolidation stresses (**Figure 4**), whereas the lowest values were measured for the granular HA-A powder, as expected from its favourable flow function. Because the internal friction angle reflects friction between internal powder layers, it is closely related to flowability and shear behaviour. It usually increases with increasing particle angularity and decreasing particle size. Interestingly, HA-B exhibited the highest internal friction angle despite showing easier flow than the cohesive HA-C powder. Although the Hausner ratios of both powders showed identical values, indicating similar flow properties, small differences in powder characteristics can change their properties. Such behaviour may be related to their morphology (**Figure 5**), because HA-B contains not only equiaxed particles but also rod-like particles, which increases angularity and internal friction [19].

The first powder (HA-A) exhibits the regular morphology of spray-dried spherical granules (D50 ~ 37 μm) with a primary crystallite size of approximately 100-150 nm. The second powder (HA-B) consists of granules with irregular shape and size (D50 ~ 4 μm); the primary crystallites vary in size and include both submicrometre and micrometre-sized rod-like particles. The third powder (HA-C) is composed mainly of small granules (D50 ~ 6 μm) and particles in the submicrometre range with nanometre-sized crystallites smaller than 100 nm.

Figure 5 Morphology of commercial powders used in this work A), B) powder HA-A; C), D) HA-B powder and E), F) HA-C powder.

To understand how the angle of internal friction affects the densities of the green bodies as well as the bulk densities after sintering, another experiment was designed in which the two selected powders were mixed in a 1:1 mass ratio. In this experiment, HA-A powder with the lowest AIF was mixed with HA-B powder, which showed the highest AIF. The powders were prepared by mixing them with pure ethanol and ZrO₂ beads in a polyethylene bottle on a roller mixer for 12 h. The resulting blend, designated HA-D, was dried at 60 °C, the beads were removed by sieving, and the powder was gently ground in an agate mortar. Such blended powder HA-D was also used for the preparation of tablets using the same procedure as for the first three sample batches.

A tablet compaction was performed on a KISTLER NCFN 2153A electromechanical pressing system using a \varnothing 36 mm die. To prepare tablets from HA-A, HA-B, and HA-C powders, an initial force of 20 kN was applied, corresponding to a pressure of 19.6 MPa. This compression pressure was sufficient to ensure the mechanical integrity and strength of the tablets for samples HA-A and HA-C; however, the HA-B samples disintegrated, and therefore, the compaction force was increased to 30 kN, which corresponded to a pressure of 29.5 MPa. The increase in pressure ensured the handling strength of HA-B tablets. More than 20 discs were prepared from each powder, sintered and used for B3B testing. The geometrical green densities of as-pressed specimens were measured from the dimensions and the weight. The average value was calculated for each set along with the standard deviation, which is shown in **Table 2**. The observed increase in green density from HA-A to HA-C, despite significant differences in flowability and internal friction, indicates that die filling behaviour is not the controlling factor. Instead, the trend is governed primarily by particle size distribution, agglomerate structure, and compressibility during compaction.

Specimens were sintered at 1300 °C for 1 h in air (furnace CLASIC CZ, spol. s.r.o., Czech Republic) at a heating rate of 10 °C / min. The average dimensions of the sintered HA specimens, measured using a digital calliper with an accuracy of 0.01 mm, are presented in Table 2. The linear shrinkage results presented in the table show that shrinkage decreased progressively from sample HA-A to HA-C, which was also reflected in the bulk density values of the individual samples after sintering (Table 4). The greatest linear shrinkage, approximately 32% in diameter and 28% in thickness, was observed for disks prepared from powder HA-A. These values corresponded to the highest bulk density, approximately 2.9 g·cm⁻³, and the highest biaxial strength, approximately 108 MPa. Similar shrinkage and bulk density values were obtained only for sample HA-D. In contrast, samples HA-B, and particularly HA-C, exhibited the lowest linear shrinkage and the lowest bulk densities after sintering.

Table 2 Average dimensions of the HA discs after sintering at 1300 °C for 1 h, together with their linear shrinkage values.

Disk	Green body density g.cm ⁻³	Bulk density 1300 °C / 1h g.cm ⁻³	Diameter linear shrinkage %	Thickness linear shrinkage %
HA-A	0.95 ± 0.02	2.87±0.02	32.36 ± 0.12	28.00 ± 2.32
HA-B	1.1 ± 0.02	2.35±0.02	23.98 ± 0.35	23.90 ± 1.95
HA-C	1.21 ± 0.02	2.08±0.03	19.07 ± 0.18	17.28 ± 1.94
HA-D	1.13 ± 0.02	2.77±0.07	29.70 ± 0.31	25.81 ± 1.68

Representative hydroxyapatite discs used for B3B testing are shown in **Figure 6**. Biaxial flexural strength (BFS) was measured at room temperature on discs sintered at 1300 °C for 1 h without any additional machining, including surface polishing and edge chamfering.

Figure 6 Hydroxyapatite discs (samples HA-B) after sintering at 1300 °C for 1h.

2.2 Characterisation

Phase analysis after sintering was carried out using Panalytical EMPYREAN DY1098 powder diffractometer with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation and a 2θ step size of 0.0130° . The XRD patterns were evaluated using the Match!© software ver. 3.12 and Crystallography Open Database (COD-Inorg 2022.11.07)[20].

The morphology of the as-received powders was investigated using a field-emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM; JEOL 7500 F, JEOL Ltd., Tokyo, Japan) operated at an accelerating voltage of 15 kV. Fractographic observations were performed using both secondary-electron and backscattered-electron imaging in a Tescan Lyra3 XMU scanning electron microscope (Tescan, Czech Republic). All specimens were carbon-coated to avoid charging during imaging.

The bulk (geometrical) density of the sintered specimens was calculated from the dimensions and weight of each sample. Young's modulus was calculated from natural frequencies determined on randomly selected discs using the impulse excitation technique with an RFDA HT1600 system (IMCE, Belgium) in accordance with the relevant standard. At least five specimens were tested for each batch, and at least five readings of the natural frequency were recorded for each specimen [21].

The biaxial flexure test, B3B, was carried out using three support balls in fixed positions and a fourth loading ball moving only in the vertical direction. The ball diameter was 17.462 mm, resulting in ~ 20 mm support diameter. Testing was performed on an Instron 8862 machine equipped with BlueHill 3 software (Instron, USA). The discs were centred and loaded at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min to the fracture. The maximum tensile stress, σ_{\max} , was calculated from the general expression in which F is the fracture force, and t is the disc thickness.

$$\sigma_{\max} = f \frac{F}{t^2} \quad (2)$$

The factor f is dimensionless and depends on the geometry of the specimen and balls, the Poisson's ratio of the material, and the details of load transfer during testing. It can be determined by linear-elastic finite element analysis. [14]

3 RESULTS

3.1 XRD Patterns

The XRD pattern of the as-received HA-A powder (Figure 7) shows broad peaks, indicating low crystallite size and partial amorphous content. Detected peaks correspond well with all hydroxyapatite reference reflections with the dominant Miller indices (hkl) 002, 211, 112 and (300) at 2θ values of

25.69°, 31.81°, 32.98°, and 33.98°, respectively. The peak shapes are typical of commercial spray-dried or precipitated HA powders. Compared with HA-A, HA-B is more crystalline and slightly coarser, which suggests either a different synthesis route or post-synthesis thermal treatment. Both powders are consistent with nanocrystalline hydroxyapatite; however, a trace amount of a secondary whitlockite phase was also detected in HA-B. The HA-C powder consists primarily of whitlockite with a significant proportion of the HA phase, and calcium carbonate peaks were also observed. The presence of calcium carbonate in this commercial powder may be explained, for example, by an unreacted fraction remaining after solid-state reaction with calcium dihydrogen phosphate. Depending on the processing conditions, this route may also lead to the formation of β -TCP [22].

XRD analysis of selected discs sintered at 1300 °C for 1 h is shown in Figure 8. In the sample labels, the letter indicates the batch, and the number indicates the order in which the specimen was measured in the B3B test. The XRD records of the sintered HA-A and HA-C specimens show only the HA phase. In contrast, the sintered HA-B sample transformed after firing into a mixture of β -TCP with a smaller fraction of HA. This behaviour is consistent with the known dehydroxylation of HA to form β -TCP under suitable conditions. The semiquantitative analysis based on the Reference Intensity Ratio (RIR) calculation using Match! software and COD reference database revealed an approximate amount of 12.5 % of hydroxyapatite, with the rest being β -TCP phase. The theoretical density based on this ratio was calculated to be 3.08 g.cm⁻³. The HA-D sample also contains both phases; however, in this case the HA phase remains dominant. The RIR calculation in this case revealed an approximate amount of 78.6 % of hydroxyapatite with the rest being β -TCP phase, thus the theoretical density for this sample was calculated to be 3.12 g.cm⁻³. Due to the very small differences in the theoretical densities of both phases present (3.14 g.cm⁻³ for HA and 3.07 g.cm⁻³ for β -TCP), the calculated theoretical densities are not very different either. Because HA-D was prepared by mixing HA-A and HA-B powders, this result is consistent with the phase composition of the two starting powders.

Figure 7 X-ray diffraction patterns of commercial powders used in this work.

Figure 8 X-ray diffraction patterns of disc samples sintered at 1300 °C for 1 hour and prepared from HA-A, HA-B, HA-C powders; HA-D was prepared from a 1:1 mixture of HA-A and HA-B. The letter indicates the batch, and the number indicates the order of B3B measurement.

3.2 Biaxial strength

The bulk-density and B3B-strength data of all specimens sintered at 1300 °C for 1 h are shown in **Table 3** and **Figure 9**. The characteristic B3B strength increased in the following order: HA-B \approx HA-C < HA-D < HA-A, with values of 37.2 ± 0.5 MPa, 38.6 ± 1.1 MPa, 106.5 ± 1.6 MPa, and 108.1 ± 1.1 MPa, respectively. The first two materials (HA-B and HA-C) showed nearly identical Weibull strength values and did not differ significantly within their standard deviations. Nevertheless, they show different relative densities, with the average value of the HA-B sample (76.4%) being about 10% denser than the HA-C sample (66.2%). The highest B3B strength was measured for discs prepared from HA-A powder, with a relative density reaching 91.4%, followed interestingly, by HA-D samples with a density of 88.7%.

Table 3 Material characteristics of HA samples sintered at 1300 °C for 1 hour.

HA material	Characteristic strength MPa	Weibull modulus (m, B3B)	E-Modulus GPa
HA-A	108.1±1.1	23.6±3.8	90.6±4.3
HA-B	37.2±0.5	18.8±3.3	45.6±2.9
HA-C	38.6±1.1	8.3±1.4	37.5±2.3
HA-D	106.5±1.6	13.1±2.0	86.2±0.2

Figure 9 Geometrical bulk densities and B3B strength of HA samples prepared from three commercial powders (HA-A, HA-B and HA-C) and from HA-D (mixture HA-A : HA-B = 1 : 1).

As can be seen from Figure 9 the strength values follow the trend of the bulk density values as expected. Assuming the theoretical density of hydroxyapatite (3.14 g.cm^{-3}), the highest porosity was determined for sample HA-C ($\sim 34\%$) and HA-B ($\sim 25\%$), while the porosity for samples HA-A and HA-D were $\sim 8\%$ and $\sim 12\%$ respective.

To evaluate strength reliability, the two-parameter Weibull distribution was used. After logarithmic transformation, the Weibull equation becomes linear, and the slope of the resulting line corresponds to the Weibull modulus describing the scatter of data. [23]

$$P_f = 1 - \exp \left[\left(- \frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^m \right] \quad (3)$$

The characteristic strength, Weibull modulus, and Young's modulus experimental values are summarised in **Table 3**. These data show that the highest Weibull modulus, i.e., the lowest data scatter, was obtained for HA-A ($m \sim 24$), followed by HA-B ($m \sim 19$) and HA-D ($m \sim 13$), whereas the lowest value was found for HA-C ($m \sim 8$). All materials exhibited monomodal Weibull distributions. The scatter of strength values for HA-A was very small, resulting in a high Weibull modulus falling in the range of about 20-30, which is considered reliable for ceramics. HA-B also showed a relatively high Weibull modulus of ~ 20 , despite its much lower characteristic strength ($\sim 36 \text{ MPa}$), which is mainly due to its higher porosity.

Figure 10 Weibull analysis of the tested HA samples.

Young's modulus was measured for all four materials by the resonance method using impulse excitation. The Young's modulus values followed the same trend as bulk density and B3B strength. The highest modulus (~90 GPa) was measured for HA-A, which also showed the highest bulk density and strength. With increasing porosity, the modulus decreased, reaching a minimum of about 38 GPa for HA-C. It is noteworthy that replacing 50 wt.% of HA-A with HA-B in sample HA-D did not result in major changes in the physical or mechanical properties compared with the pure spray-dried material. The larger scatter of the HA-D values can be attributed to specimen preparation and the somewhat higher porosity, both of which increase the number of defects and thus the probability of fracture. Lopes et al [24] studied the elastic properties (dynamic Young's and shear moduli) of rectangular HA specimens by impulse excitation of vibration according to ASTM C1259-96. Pure HA samples sintered at 1300 °C for 1 h showed low porosity (~5 %) and a high Young's modulus of 109 GPa. Increasing the temperature to 1350 °C led to higher porosity and a lower elastic modulus. Although the authors did not report a change in phase composition, partial decomposition of HA to TCP may already occur at such temperatures and could explain these changes. The elastic properties of dense hydroxyapatite thin films prepared by radio-frequency sputtering were also studied by Snyders et al. using nanoindentation and comparison with *ab-initio* calculations. They reported a measured modulus of 147 ± 10 GPa, approximately 10% higher than the calculated value. Differences in reported Young's modulus values can therefore be attributed to factors such as bulk density or porosity, phase transformation and phase purity, crystallinity, and grain size [25], [26].

3.3 Fractography and microstructure analysis

The fracture origin in the discs was identified near the centre of the specimens at the tensile side, and the cracks propagated perpendicular to the local tensile-stress direction, as expected. After fracture initiation, the propagating cracks produced two-, three-, four-, and multiple-fragment failure patterns. For HA-A, three-fold failure was the dominant mode (45% of specimens), followed by four-fold failure (32%) and five-fold failure (23%). In HA-B, the situation changed markedly: two-fold failure dominated in 77% of discs, whereas three-fold failure was observed in only 23% of cases and no additional modes were found. A similar trend was observed for HA-C, where two-fold failure prevailed

(64%), followed by three-fold failure (32%) and four-fold failure (5%). Examples of these failure modes are shown in **Figure 11**.

Figure 11 Fracture patterns in HA discs with the highest and lowest B3B strength: HA-A (left) and HA-B (right).

The results show that the location of fracture initiation is independent of the final number of fracture fragments, which are apparently related to crack propagation; i.e., the number of fragments is related to the stored elastic energy and fracture toughness. Samples HA-B and HA-C, which had higher porosity and lower biaxial strength, preferentially exhibited lower-fold failure patterns than the denser and stronger HA-A specimens. Although all specimens were subjected to the same biaxial loading configuration, the observed fracture patterns indicate that crack initiation was governed primarily by microstructural defects rather than by the ideal stress field alone. In the more porous and lower-strength HA specimens, fracture initiated at a lower applied stress from a dominant critical flaw, causing rapid stress relaxation and suppressing the branching of the main crack. This interpretation is consistent with defect-controlled fracture behaviour reported for porous hydroxyapatite ceramics under biaxial flexure. [27] As a result, these specimens preferentially exhibited simpler fracture patterns with lower fold symmetry. Similar behaviour was reported for commercial alumina discs, in which the number of fracture fragments increased with strength owing to higher stored elastic energy. [14] A comparable explanation has also been proposed for dense Si_3N_4 ceramics, where the higher applied force required for failure can cause secondary disc damage due to the high contact pressure at the supporting balls [28].

Fractographic analysis was performed on the fracture surfaces of selected discs representing each material set (**Figure 12**). SEM observations were carried out using both secondary-electron and backscattered-electron imaging modes. For each set, the disc with the highest measured strength was selected for analysis. The images are shown with the tensile side facing upward, and the fracture origin is marked by a yellow ellipse in the centre of each micrograph. As noted above, the specimens fractured into several fragments, typically initiated by surface defects, because failure in most cases started at or near the surface rather than in the bulk. In the present study, all discs were tested in the as-sintered condition without additional grinding or machining. Surface defects may therefore have originated either from imperfect specimen preparation or from flaws located close to the surface.

Figure 12 SEM analysis of the fracture surface of fragmented specimens. The fracture origin is marked with a yellow dashed ellipse.

The typical microstructures observed on the fracture surfaces of the four investigated bioceramic materials, HA-A, HA-B, HA-C, and HA-D, are shown in **Figure 13**. Microstructural analysis of the discs revealed that HA-A contained the lowest number of pores among all samples. Most pores were closed and located primarily at grain boundaries, with sizes of approximately 3-5 μm , although regions of lower local density and larger voids of about 20-50 μm were also observed. By contrast, HA-B exhibited a highly porous microstructure with a relatively homogeneous distribution of pore sizes similar to those observed in HA-A. High porosity was also observed in HA-C, whereas the microstructure of HA-D more closely resembled that of HA-A. HA-A contained the largest grains, typically about 15-30 μm in size and irregular in shape; grains of similar size were also observed in HA-D. The finest grains, approximately 4 μm , and the most homogeneous microstructure were found in HA-C, while HA-B displayed a clearly bimodal morphology. In HA-B, well-sintered larger grains were connected to smaller grains of about 2-6 μm in the presence of numerous small pores. Fewer but still important, larger, irregular, and elongated pores or voids were also observed. These pores appear to form a percolating network with high connectivity, likely due to the powder's high surface area, its lower flowability and rearrangement in the steel die, and subsequent pore-pore coalescence. Only small differences in bulk density (**Table 2**) were observed, with the highest value for HA-A and the lowest for HA-C. The microstructural development is also reflected in the B3B results, where HA-A and HA-D showed very similar characteristic strengths (~ 107 MPa), whereas HA-B and HA-C exhibited much lower characteristic values of about 37 MPa.

Figure 13 SEM micrographs of bioceramic samples HA-A, HA-B, HA-C, and HA-D taken from fracture surfaces of discs sintered at 1300 °C for 1 h.

To obtain a comprehensive overview of the microstructure of the samples, cross-section surfaces were prepared by grinding and polishing for the SEM analysis (**Figure 14**). The images were used to calculate the total porosity using image analysis in ImageJ software. The image analysis results showed that the lowest total porosity was calculated for sample HA-D, followed by samples HA-A, HA-B and HA-C. The porosity values increased in the following order: 5.0% HA-D < 6.8% HA-A < 22.8% HA-B < 43.2% HA-C. The porosity results for the samples after sintering at 1300 °C for 1h, calculated from the relative density, differ from the values calculated using image analysis. According to the density measurement after sintering, the HA-A sample had the lowest porosity of 8.6%, followed by the HA-D sample with 11.3%, the HA-B sample with 23.6%, and the HA-C sample with 33.8%. The observed difference between porosity values obtained by image analysis and relative density results primarily from stereological limitations and sampling effects, rather than from simple 2D and 3D resolution. Image analysis can detect both open and closed pores that intersect the polished section. This provides a local area fraction that approximates the true 3D porosity under the assumptions of isotropy, statistical representativeness, and isolated pores. However, this is not the case for heterogeneous microstructures. Relative density measurements, on the other hand, reflect the pore volume, but their accuracy depends on the correct theoretical density. However, it can be affected by inaccessible pores or limitations of the measurement method, especially for samples with high total porosity and open structure. The relative density measurement method is usually much more accurate and better reflects the final state of porosity in the samples.

Figure 14 SEM micrographs of polished cross-section surfaces of HA-A, HA-B, HA-C, and HA-D discs sintered at 1300 °C for 1 h.

3.4 Discussion

The literature on disc-based biaxial flexure testing consistently identifies residual porosity and defect population as the dominant factors controlling measured strength. These attributes strongly affect the biaxial flexural strength of hydroxyapatite, β -tricalcium phosphate (β -TCP), and related calcium phosphate ceramics, often more strongly than bulk density alone. The critical issue is not only the amount of porosity, but also its character, including whether pores are open or closed, their size, and their connectivity. Porosity itself depends on several factors, most notably the characteristics of the starting powder, the shaping route, the formation of secondary defects during heat treatment, and the sintering conditions. Biaxial strength is also influenced by microstructure, phase composition, and the presence of sintering additives. For this reason, the literature data summarized in **Table 4** differ substantially. Another important factor affecting the measured strength is the choice of the biaxial test method.

The highest biaxial strength identified in the literature survey was reported for a CaP-ZrO₂ composite modified with SiO₂, where a maximum characteristic strength of approximately 268 MPa was achieved at porosity below 1% after pressure less sintering at 1200 °C. [29] In that study, silica acted not merely as a filler, but as an additive that modified phase evolution, densification, and microstructure development. By contrast, the addition of bioglass to hydroxyapatite promoted the formation of β -TCP up to 1250 °C and α -TCP at higher sintering temperatures. [30]. It was reported that bioglass additions of up to 5 wt.% significantly disrupted sintering, delayed densification at higher temperatures, and caused cracking during sintering. At 1300 °C, HA samples containing 2.5 wt. % bioglass reached a biaxial strength of 18.5 MPa, whereas pure HA reached 20.9 ± 2.7 MPa. More generally, the biaxial strength of HA specimens depends strongly on processing route, sintering conditions, and test configuration. HA specimens prepared by cold pressing at 33 MPa and sintered at 1025 °C for 120 min showed a very low biaxial flexural strength of 4.9 ± 0.6 MPa at 59% porosity. [31] Increasing the sintering temperature to 1220 °C and 1360 °C increased the strength to 42.2 ± 8.2 MPa at 24% fracture porosity and to 97 ± 15 MPa at 8% fracture porosity, respectively. [27]. These specimens were measured using a ring-on-ring fixture and were prepared from the biomedical-grade commercial hydroxyapatite powder HAP-200 (Taihei Chemical Industrials Co., Osaka, Japan). Interestingly, Meganack et al. [32] reported that lower uniaxial cold-pressing conditions (6.9 MPa for 1 min) produced higher biaxial strength under comparable sintering conditions. They measured an average characteristic biaxial strength of 134.9 ± 0.4 MPa for nearly fully dense HA specimens tested in a piston-on-three-ball configuration. The relative porosity of those samples was only about 2.7%. They also used a commercial

HA powder, but from a different manufacturer (Berkeley Advanced Biomaterials, San Francisco, CA) with an average particle size of about 0.85 μm . Because the sintering temperature exceeded the thermal stability limit of HA, phase analysis of those discs also revealed minor secondary α -TCP and β -TCP phases. In the study by Fan et al. [27] no detectable secondary phases were reported either in the starting powders or in bulk samples sintered at 1100 and 1200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. However, at 1360 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ a weak peak at $2\theta \approx 31^{\circ}$ was observed and associated with the presence of β -TCP.

Table 4 Review of biaxial strength data for bioceramic materials relevant to this study.

Material	Sintering conditions	Bulk density g.cm^{-3}	Biaxial Strength (MPa)	Wei bull Mod ulus	Testing Method	Reference
HA	1300	3.08	20.9 ± 2.7	-	Biaxial flexural strength	[30]
HA-2.5 wt.% bioglass	1300	2.87	18.5	-	Biaxial flexural strength	[30]
HA-TCP	1200	2.95	~ 39	-	Piston on three ball test	[33]
50/50 HA/ β -TCP 75/25 HA/ β -TCP	HP 40 MPa 1100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ 30 min	2.93 ± 0.1 2.89 ± 0.05	38.17 ± 4.99 43.59 ± 8.31	-	the ball-on-three-balls method (ASTM C1161)	[34]
β -TCP	1100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ 2 h		28.4 ± 2.8	11.8		[35]
HAp:ZrO ₂ , 20 wt% silica	1200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$		268 MPa		biaxial strength bending	[29]
HA Cold pressing 33 MPa	1025 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ 120 min	Volume fracture porosity 59%	4.9 ± 0.6	11.9 ± 0.8	ring-on-ring test fixture	[31]
HA Cold pressing 33 MPa	1360 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ 240 min	Volume fracture porosity 8%	97 ± 15	6.8 ± 0.4	ring-on-ring test fixture	[27]
HA Cold pressing 33 MPa	1220 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ 60 min	Volume fracture porosity 24%	42.2 ± 8.2	6.1 ± 0.6	ring-on-ring test fixture	[27]
HA Uniaxial cold pressing 6.9 MPa for 1 min	1360 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ 240 min	Relative density $97.7 \pm 0.7\%$	134.9 ± 0.4	11.9 ± 0.7	Piston on three ball biaxial flexure testing	[32]
β -TCP Uniaxial cold pressing	1200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ 240 min	Relative density $63.9 \pm 3.2\%$	23.6 ± 0.4	9.3 ± 2.0	Piston on three ball biaxial flexure testing	[32]

6.9 MPa for 1 min						
60/40 HA/β-TCP Uniaxial cold pressing 6.9 MPa for 1 min	1200 °C 240 min	Relative density 69.1 \pm 1.4%	24.0 \pm 0.2	12.6 \pm 1.5	Piston on three ball biaxial flexure testing	[32]

In general, the presence of β -TCP tends to reduce biaxial flexural strength. For example, a composition containing 40% β -TCP in an HA matrix and sintered at 1200 °C for 4 h reached only about 24 MPa at a relative density of approximately 69% when tested in a piston-on-three-balls fixture [32]. These results were comparable to those obtained for pure β -TCP. When hot pressing at 1100 °C for 30 min was used, HA samples containing 25% β -TCP reached about 44 MPa, whereas samples containing 50% β -TCP reached a slightly lower value of about 38 MPa when tested by the ball-on-three-balls method. [33] As discussed above, the strength of HA samples is influenced not only by porosity or relative density, but also by sintering conditions and, importantly, by powder origin. Powder origin affects phase composition, the shaping process and green density, and sintering behaviour, for example, through minor impurities.

This study focused on the consistent characterization of the starting powders and on their influence on biaxial strength, together with Weibull statistical analysis. The results show that, despite identical sintering conditions, the measured strength varies markedly among the investigated powders (**Table 3**). Powder origin and powder properties, therefore, play an important role in the repeatability and reliability of the processing route, which is highly relevant from a technological point of view.

Although the present results clearly show that commercial powder origin strongly affects the densification behaviour, microstructure, and biaxial strength of hydroxyapatite ceramics, the study has several limitations. The investigated powders differed not only in origin but also in phase composition, particle morphology, particle size distribution, and rheological behaviour; therefore, the individual effects of each parameter could not be unambiguously separated. In addition, different compaction pressures were used to obtain sufficiently robust green bodies, which reflects practical processing conditions but introduces an additional variable affecting green density and flaw population. Fractographic analysis was carried out on selected high-strength specimens and, therefore, should be interpreted as illustrative rather than statistically representative of all critical defects governing failure. Since the discs were tested in the as-sintered condition, without machining or edge finishing, the measured B3B strength includes contributions from surface-related flaws in addition to bulk microstructural defects. Moreover, the blending approach was examined only for a 1:1 HA-A/HA-B composition, and further work is needed to establish a broader relationship between composition, processing, and properties.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The study showed that the origin and properties of commercial hydroxyapatite powders strongly influenced the densification, microstructure, and biaxial strength of sintered ceramics. Samples HA-A and HA-D achieved the highest bulk density, B3B strength, and Young's modulus, while HA-B and HA-C showed lower density and markedly lower strength. The best performance was obtained for HA-A, with a characteristic strength of 108.1 MPa, Weibull modulus of 23.6, and Young's modulus of 90.6 GPa, whereas HA-B and HA-C reached only about 37–39 MPa. Overall, the results confirmed that powder flowability, compressibility, particle morphology, and resulting porosity are key factors controlling the mechanical reliability of hydroxyapatite bioceramics.

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Data Availability

Data supporting the findings of this study are available in the Zenodo repository at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20238466>.

Acknowledgments

The financial support of the Agency for Research and Development Support under contract No APVV-21-0173, Slovak Grant Agency VEGA (grant number 1/0132/26 and 1/0070/22) and the support of the project Increasing the Capacities and Competences of Universities in Research, Development and Innovation ("ACCORD") ITMS2014+:313021X329, co-funded by the European Regional Development Fund, is gratefully acknowledged. This work was also financially supported by the project "Mechanical Engineering of Biological and Bio-inspired Systems", funded under project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004634 by the Johannes Amos Comenius Programme, call Excellent Research.

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